

Unsupervised Learning and Process Analysis for Sensor Data Validation in the IIoT

ERIK JOHANNES HUSOM, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

ARDA GOKNIL, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

FELIX MANNHARDT, KIT-AR, London, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

SIMEON TVERDAL, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

SAGAR SEN, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

PHU NGUYEN, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) with the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) has transformed industrial processes, enhancing productivity, quality control, and operational efficiency. However, ensuring the precision and reliability of sensor-generated data remains a critical challenge due to the evolving nature of industrial processes and the limitations of conventional validation methods. Traditional rule-based and supervised learning approaches struggle to adapt to process shifts, drifts, and novel anomalies, making sensor data validation an ongoing issue. This article introduces UDAVA (Unsupervised Learning Approach using Process Mining for Sensor Data Validation in IIoT), a novel AI-driven pipeline designed to automate the identification of reference patterns in sensor data and validate subsequent production cycles by recognizing deviations from expected behaviors. UDAVA employs a multi-stage process that includes preprocessing sensor data, clustering recurring patterns, and assessing deviations. It supports semi-supervised learning by integrating manual labels where available, improving interpretability and accuracy. One of UDAVA's key strengths lies in its ability to extract features from sensor data rather than relying on raw time series similarity, making it robust against noise and diverse process variations. Additionally, UDAVA integrates process mining techniques—process discovery and conformance checking—to enhance its ability to detect even subtle anomalies and deviations in industrial workflows. We conduct a comprehensive evaluation of UDAVA using three industrial datasets, demonstrating its effectiveness in identifying high-level process behaviors, detecting process shifts and drifts, and ensuring data validation across multiple production cycles. The results highlight UDAVA's adaptability across different industrial processes, making it a valuable tool for optimizing operations and ensuring sensor data reliability in IIoT environments.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Unsupervised learning, IIoT, process mining, data reliability

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Authors' Contact Information: Erik Johannes Husom, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway; e-mail: erik.johannes.husom@sintef.no; Arda Goknil (corresponding author), SINTEF, Oslo, Norway; e-mail: arda.goknil@sintef.no; Felix Mannhardt, KIT-AR, London, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland; e-mail: felix.mannhardt@kit-ar.com; Simeon Tverdal, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway; e-mail: simeon.tverdal@sintef.no; Sagar Sen, SINTEF, Oslo, Norway; e-mail: sagar.sen@sintef.no; Phu Nguyen, SINTEF, Oslo, Oslo, Norway; e-mail: phu.nguyen@sintef.no.

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1 Introduction

The rapid evolution of Industry 4.0, driven by the **Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)** and **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, presents new opportunities and challenges in optimizing industrial processes. IIoT's integration of advanced sensors into industrial environments allows real-time data acquisition. However, effectively validating sensor data within AI-enabled IIoT systems is complex [37, 80–82, 92]. In these systems, sensors continuously generate vast, nuanced data streams crucial for decision-making and automation. Ensuring data fidelity in dynamic industrial processes is a formidable challenge, surpassing the capabilities of traditional data validation methods.

Machine Learning (ML) applications within the realm of IIoT play a pivotal role in harnessing sensor data for multifaceted purposes [45, 47, 66, 67, 80, 83, 96]. These applications undergo a training phase where they ingest and analyze sensor data. Their objectives encompass both real-time decision-making and retrospective analysis of product defects and production failures. One of the key attributes of ML applications in IIoT is their heightened sensitivity to transitions in repetitive process behavior. These transitions encompass a spectrum of scenarios, including *normal operation*, *process shifts*, and *drifts* [31]. These terms refer to distinct patterns of variation in the data, and they are time-ordered trends that deviate from the intended target value of measured process parameters. These factors exert a discernible influence on the capacity to manufacture goods within predefined specifications.

An instance of a process shift commonly encountered originates from the initial manual configuration of the manufacturing line. This configuration, which includes tasks such as sensor calibration [63], becomes necessary each time a new production lot, signifying a substantial quantity of goods or parts, commences. In contrast, a process drift represents a gradual alteration of the manufacturing process that transpires over time. The origins of process drifts are typically traced back to sensor malfunctions [58], tool wear [86], variations in workpiece surface quality [52], and anomalies in chip evacuation mechanisms [16]. Detecting a process drift in the presence of high-volume and high-velocity multivariate sensor data poses a formidable challenge, as it may become obscured by concurrent deviations in the process dynamics. Thus, sensor data validation and process pattern identification are the keys to revealing process shifts and drifts.

Although considerable research has been devoted to data validation [38], only a few approaches can be adopted to identify process behavior in IIoT. However, these few approaches have specific constraints that limit their applicability and generalizability in the IIoT context. For instance, deep learning techniques like **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)**, **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)**, and autoencoders have demonstrated their efficacy in identifying abnormal behaviors [59], but constrained by their interpretability and a strong reliance on extensive, high-quality training datasets. These methodologies predominantly center on detecting anomalies based on residual errors, offering limited support for the comprehensive identification of general process behaviors within the IIoT context. On the other hand, unsupervised outlier detection methods [13, 57, 75] resemble classification-oriented approaches often employed to identify abnormal behaviors. These methods are predominantly geared toward binary classifications, categorizing data points as either inliers or outliers, and they do not specifically address the broader spectrum of process behaviors. Conventional methodologies for clustering time series data depend on measuring raw data similarity and employ distance metrics to partition time series into sub-sequences [3]. Nonetheless, the application of Euclidean distance [26] in this context is beset by certain constraints, including its

rigid handling of time series of fixed sizes and susceptibility to the adverse effects of noise and distortion. **Dynamic time warping (DTW)** [65] represents a notable improvement, mitigating these limitations to some extent. However, it still has challenges in accurately aligning time series data with varying lengths and shapes, particularly in scenarios with noisy or sparse data. It may struggle with computational efficiency when applied to real-time streaming data.

The acquisition of extensive and rapidly changing multivariate sensor data in industrial operations poses a formidable challenge for human operators. It entails the demanding task of discerning a wide array of distinctive patterns within the data and monitoring their deviations (including shifts and drifts in the industrial process) across numerous production cycles. Ensuring the precision and reliability of sensor-generated data remains a critical issue, as conventional rule-based and supervised learning methods often struggle with evolving process behaviors and novel anomalies. Therefore, our research endeavors to explore the feasibility of engineering an AI system with a dual purpose: (a) the automated identification of *reference patterns* that encapsulate various modes of process behavior within sensor data extracted from an initial reference production cycle and (b) the subsequent validation of data in subsequent production cycles through the recognition of the reappearance of these reference patterns. We aim to provide a scalable and adaptive solution for sensor data validation in IIoT environments, overcoming the limitations of traditional techniques in handling dynamic industrial processes.

In this article, we propose, apply, and assess an unsupervised ML pipeline using clustering and process mining for sensor data validation in IIoT (UDAVA), automatically discovering process behavior patterns in sensor data streams acquired during repetitive industrial processes. UDAVA employs a multi-stage approach, starting with data preprocessing, where subsequences are extracted from raw time series data using a sliding window technique. These subsequences are transformed into feature vectors using statistical measures such as *mean*, *median*, *gradient*, *variance*, *range*, and *frequency strength*. The pipeline further incorporates unsupervised learning techniques, primarily clustering algorithms, to categorize the feature vectors into clusters representing distinct process behavior patterns. The choice of clustering algorithm is configurable, allowing adaptability to various industrial scenarios. UDAVA also supports semi-supervised learning by integrating manual labels when available, improving interpretability and accuracy. Following clustering, UDAVA computes a deviation metric to measure the extent of deviation of operational data from reference data, serving as a baseline for ideal process behavior. This metric enables the detection of anomalies and deviations in real-time industrial processes.

To address noise in the data, UDAVA prunes short segments and merges or divides them based on the closest cluster center in feature space. This noise reduction step we call sequence pruning enhances the interpretability and reliability of the results. UDAVA provides an event log, which records the segments' start and end times with corresponding labels. This event log is utilized for further process analysis and quality control efforts. UDAVA also allows users to specify boundary segments and time thresholds for partitioning the event log into cases, facilitating two process mining tasks: *process discovery* and *conformance checking*. The integration of process discovery and conformance checking in UDAVA is essential despite the existence of the deviation metric. It offers a holistic view of industrial processes, aiding in identifying underlying process models and their adherence to real-world executions. While the deviation metric primarily focuses on assessing data-driven deviations, process discovery uncovers the intrinsic structure of processes, ensuring a comprehensive understanding. Conformance checking, on the other hand, verifies the alignment of actual process executions with these models, offering a mechanism for early detection of non-compliance and bottlenecks. Together, they enable continuous improvement, quality assurance, and resource optimization, making UDAVA an indispensable tool for industries seeking enhanced productivity, cost-effectiveness, and product quality in industrial processes.

In the evaluation of UDAVA, we investigate, based on three industrial datasets, the following **Research Questions (RQs)**:

- **RQ1.** *To what extent can UDAVA discover behavior patterns in IIoT sensor data for a reference production cycle?*
- **RQ2.** *Does comparing process behavior patterns reveal process shifts and drifts in subsequent production cycles?*
- **RQ3.** *To what extent can UDAVA reveal and be used to analyze the high-level repetitive process behavior on an aggregate level of several production cycles?*

Our evaluation focuses on validating sensor data in repetitive industrial operations, analyzing process deviations, and uncovering high-level behavioral trends. The evaluation examined UDAVA's ability to detect key process stages, assess deviations from expected behaviors, and visualize process dynamics through process mining techniques. Results show that UDAVA accurately identifies major process activities with high precision while highlighting challenges in detecting boundary transitions. Additionally, by analyzing process behavior over time, UDAVA successfully captures process shifts and drifts, demonstrating its robustness in detecting operational variations. These findings underscore the capability of UDAVA to enhance sensor data validation and provide insights for industrial process monitoring and optimization.

This article builds upon our previous work presented at CAIN'22 [46] and our tool demonstration at IoT'23 [44], refining and extending key ideas. We enhance the UDAVA pipeline by integrating *process discovery and conformance checking*, enabling the identification of patterns, anomalies, and deviations while supporting root cause analysis for industrial process optimization. Additionally, we introduce two new pipeline stages: sequence pruning, which filters out irrelevant or short-lived data segments to focus on meaningful patterns, and event log creation, which facilitates visualization, validation, and analysis of production cycles to ensure activity order and duration align with expectations. Finally, we provide new empirical evidence demonstrating UDAVA's effectiveness and efficiency through evaluations on three real-world IIoT datasets.

To summarize, our contributions include:

- **UDAVA pipeline:** The article introduces a novel approach designed for the automatic validation of sensor data in repetitive industrial processes. This pipeline offers a systematic framework for data preprocessing, clustering, and anomaly detection, tailored to the specific needs of IIoT applications. UDAVA can be downloaded at <https://sintef-9012.github.io/Udava/>
- **Integration of Process Discovery and Conformance:** One key contribution is the incorporation of process discovery and conformance checking within the UDAVA pipeline. This feature enables the identification of patterns and anomalies in the production process, adding a layer of interpretability and actionable insights to the sensor data validation process. It allows for a deeper understanding of deviations and their implications in the context of IIoT.
- **Comprehensive Evaluation with Industrial Datasets:** We comprehensively evaluate UDAVA with real-world industrial datasets, employing various metrics like precision, recall, accuracy, and event log scores across diverse industrial domains. Our rigorous experimentation and analysis showcase the method's effectiveness in detecting process deviations and anomalies, providing valuable insights for industrial process optimization and quality control.

The article is structured as follows. Sections 2 and 3 present the background and related work. In Section 4, we describe UDAVA. Section 5 reports on the evaluation. Section 6 concludes the article.

2 Background

2.1 Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning in ML involves algorithms discerning patterns within datasets without human intervention or labeled data. It is crucial for exploratory data analysis, behavior profiling, predictive maintenance, customer segmentation, cross-selling strategies, and image recognition. Key techniques include clustering (grouping data points into clusters) and outlier detection (identifying exceptional data points).

- *Clustering methods*, e.g., K-means [60], Mean Shift [20], DBSCAN [30], and OPTICS [5].
- *Outlier detection*, e.g., Local Outlier Factor [13], DBSCAN [30], and Isolation Forest [57].

One unsupervised method is to cluster observations in a dataset based on their characteristics to find similarities within clusters and dissimilarities between them. Among many alternatives (e.g., Manhattan distance, cosine similarity, and Mahalanobis distance), Euclidean distance measures observation similarity by computing the straight-line distance between two points in a multidimensional space, assuming equal weight for all dimensions and independence between features. UDAVA uses several clustering algorithms like K-means [60], mini-batch K-means [76], Mean Shift [20], DBSCAN [30], OPTICS [5], and affinity propagation [34].

UDAVA defaults to K-means [60], a centroid-based clustering algorithm where each cluster is represented by a centroid vector. The algorithm requires a predefined number of clusters and iteratively refines assignments by recalculating centroids and reassigning data points based on proximity. This process continues until convergence or reaching a set iteration limit. Each cluster is labeled from 1 to N , where N is the total number of clusters. To enhance efficiency, K-means uses mini-batches of randomly sampled data to accelerate convergence and handle large datasets.

2.2 Process Discovery and Conformance Checking

Process mining is an analytical approach that examines real-world process behavior by establishing connections between recorded events during the execution of process instances and the corresponding performed activities [93]. It encompasses tasks like process discovery [6], which builds process models from event data, and conformance checking [19], which evaluates process executions against a reference model.

Process mining hinges on the assumption that timestamps correspond to specific activities within individual process instances [93], commonly observed in traditional business workflows. The industrial processes in this study primarily pertain to the manufacturing domain, differing from conventional business processes, albeit sharing similarities in process management and automation approaches [74]. However, when applied to industrial contexts like manufacturing, data landscape differs, presenting challenges for process mining [87]. While major production milestones may be logged, finer-grained operational steps often remain undocumented [87]. While **Programmable Logic Controller (PLC)** data can offer timestamps for significant activities, capturing detailed process nuances may necessitate leveraging sensor data inference techniques, as proposed in this study.

In summary, achieving a fine-grained level of event data is imperative to enable process mining at the level of detailed work in industrial contexts, such as manufacturing environments. This approach has the potential to offer fresh insights into the actual execution of tasks on the shop floor, moving beyond the scope of coarse-grained process steps.

3 Related Work

3.1 Sensor Data Validation for Process Behavior in IIoT Data

In IIoT, process behavior, such as manufacturing turbine discs, is repetitive, leading to various sensor data behaviors from normal operations to process shifts and drifts [31]. Traditional methods,

like expert systems, rely on predefined rules to identify anomalies but struggle with complex or unfamiliar deviations [41, 42]. In contrast, UDAVA utilizes feature-based clustering, enabling the detection of diverse anomalies in sensor data from repetitive industrial processes in the IIoT without predefined rules. Statistical analysis, supported by various studies [18, 71, 73, 97, 98], employs robust statistical measures like mean, median, and standard deviation to detect process deviations. Additionally, **statistical process control (SPC)** [68] enables real-time monitoring through control charts but may miss context-specific anomalies or struggle with evolving data patterns and large datasets. Time series analysis has also been used extensively but may falter with sudden disruptions and require extensive historical data [1, 40]. UDAVA overcomes these limitations by using feature-based clustering for efficient anomaly detection, supporting real-time validation, and adapting to changing data patterns and contextual anomalies.

Data-driven methods, particularly neural networks like RNNs, CNNs, and LSTMs, excel in modeling time series data for sensor validation. For example, Elnour et al. [28] demonstrated the effectiveness of Auto-Associative Neural Networks in HVAC system sensor validation, while Darvishi et al. [24] introduced a neural network-based architecture for sensor data validation. Al et al. [2] conducted a review of IoT data anomaly detection, emphasizing ML and deep learning models. Despite their potential, these methods have limitations [91], including the need for substantial labeled data and challenges in adapting to evolving sensor faults or novel anomalies. In contrast, UDAVA employs unsupervised learning to detect anomalies without extensive labeled data, adapting to evolving sensor faults and identifying novel anomalies in sensor data.

In IIoT, evolving sensor data from process behavior can be validated using redundant sensors, where sensors observing the same process offer redundancy. This redundancy, whether *physical* or *analytical*, ensures data continuity in case of sensor failure but adds complexity and cost. However, physical redundancy can overlook simultaneous systematic errors, while analytical models may struggle with unmodeled complexities. Recent research [4, 43, 69, 85, 100] highlights these challenges. *Data reconciliation* [23] enhances reliability by aligning measurements from various sensors (e.g., in studies on smart structures [35] and wired drill pipes [89]), but non-linear sensor interactions and scaling pose challenges in multi-sensor systems. UDAVA addresses these issues by leveraging the repetitive nature of data in production cycles, validating data against a reference cycle to detect process shifts and drifts without relying on redundancy or reconciliation methods.

DTW [65] aids in sensor data validation by aligning temporal sequences for comparison, potentially revealing latent similarities or differences in sensor outputs. Shape Dynamic Time Warping (shapeDTW) [99] enhances match accuracy by considering local structural information. However, the main limitation of DTW lies in its potential to mistakenly align two temporal points with different local structures, leading to the misclassification of anomalies and missing subtle but significant deviations in time series sensor data. UDAVA addresses this by clustering time series data based on summary statistics, independent of minor temporal sequence differences. Yet, UDAVA's clusters may not always match expert-identified behavioral modes. To improve this, we introduce a semi-supervised feature by initializing cluster centers using domain knowledge, allowing convergence to realistic behavioral modes across subsequent production cycles with minimal labeling effort.

3.2 Process Discovery and Conformance Checking for IIoT Data

We provide a concise overview of relevant research in the process mining domain, focusing on process discovery and conformance checking with sensor data or lower-level events. Previous studies have applied process mining to low-level events [25, 95] or IoT sensor data [11, 48, 55], encountering significant challenges [11, 12, 48]. Low-level events are often subject to event abstraction techniques [95], aggregating them into higher-level events. However, this process becomes more complex with sensor-derived time series data due to their volume, rapid generation rate, and

inherent noise, as underscored in challenge C13 by Janiesch et al. [48]. Connecting sensor data to existing event logs is also challenging [12], with recent efforts aiming to bridge this gap [39]. Research on sensor-enhanced process mining typically falls into two categories.

- **Event detection approaches** identify significant events in time series data and annotate them with process activity labels [25]. These approaches have been explored in various domains, including smart homes [17, 27, 33, 49], healthcare [33, 90], smart products [94], machine-generated data [15], and manufacturing [9, 62, 77]. In lab-based manufacturing, interactive event detection has proven useful for initial sensor data analysis when combined with domain expertise [78]. When conventional process events are unavailable, detected events are grouped into process cases using heuristics or domain-specific knowledge [49], while unsupervised methods segment sensor streams into cases [14, 15, 29, 64]. For instance, Esposito et al. [29] refine an initial event subdivision through iterative case merging, Mayr et al. [64] apply clustering to synthetic manufacturing data, and Brzychczyet al. [14, 15] leverage domain knowledge of machine sensor thresholds for segmentation.
- **Context augmentation approaches** enrich conventional process event logs with additional context using time series data, which is considered exogenous to the event log [8]. Unlike event detection, these approaches do not assume that sensor data captures process events but rather influences process behavior, such as ordering, choices, or timing. Exogenous data is applied in various areas, including concept drift detection [88], decision rule extraction [7], and exploring correlations between clinical data and activities [8, 22].
- **Conformance checking approaches** compare detected event sequences from sensor data with a reference process model to assess deviations from expected behavior. Seiger et al. [79] highlight the need for probabilistic matching due to potential event detection ambiguities. Additionally, conformance checking has been used to validate event detection quality when a normative model is available [72], an approach we incorporate in our evaluation. Beyond validation, sensor data can also be integrated into process models for process execution and enactment, as demonstrated in [33, 51].

Some proposals aim to connect process data with sensor data, such as the DataStream extensions for XES [61], which suggest integrating sensor data into the XES format (although its suitability for this purpose has been questioned [12]). The DataStream framework allows the storage of both raw sensor data and data processed by UDAVA. Our approach does not assume the recording of specific process activities, but DataStream could be used to store the resulting event log.

Our approach differs from context augmentation methods as we do not assume access to a conventional event log. Regarding event detection, most prior research in sensor data and process mining focuses on less structured domains like smart homes and smart spaces [29, 49, 56], where sensor data is often discrete (e.g., motion detection [29, 49]), making these approaches unsuitable for our industrial use cases. In the manufacturing and machinery domain [14, 15, 64, 72, 77, 78, 88], most studies [9, 72, 77, 78, 88] do not employ unsupervised learning as UDAVA does. Among unsupervised methods, Bayomie et al. [9] merely log sensor value changes without abstracting them into domain events. Mayr et al. [64] present a high-level algorithm sketch without real-world validation. Brzychczy et al. [14, 15] propose an unsupervised approach tailored to long-wall mining, leveraging machine constraints specific to coal mining, which do not generalize to our use cases.

4 UDAVA Approach

UDAVA is a multi-stage, unsupervised ML pipeline designed to address the challenges of sensor data validation in IIoT environments. This section explains each pipeline stage (starting from data

Fig. 1. Overview of UDAVA. Sensor data coupled with optional annotations are used to create a cluster model. This model, once established, can be deployed to process and validate incoming data streams. Continuous sequences of labels within the data are amalgamated into distinct segments, which subsequently undergo rigorous sequence pruning. The outcome of this process is a structured sequence comprising start and completion events. These events are instrumental in generating an event log, which, in turn, becomes a vital resource for conducting both process discovery and conformance-checking analyses.

preprocessing to clustering and anomaly detection). The process in Figure 1 presents an overview of UDAVA. The main stages of the approach are as follows:

- (1) **Data preprocessing.** The initial stage involves partitioning reference (training) time series data into subsequences and extracting statistical features. These features form output feature vectors, representing the subsequences. The training dataset should include data from optimal production cycles as a benchmark for subsequent comparisons with data originating from

subsequent production cycles. Additionally, the first stage accepts annotated data, aiding cluster model creation and refinement for pattern discovery.

- (2) **Model creation.** In this stage, cluster analysis is applied to the feature vectors, assigning each feature vector to a cluster. The outcome is a model with multiple cluster centers, each defining a distinct process behavior pattern. If annotated data is made available during Stage 1, UDAVA uses these annotations as initial cluster centers (provided that the chosen cluster algorithm accommodates such input), enabling the model to be guided by human expertise and prior knowledge when establishing the initial behavior patterns.
- (3) **Inference.** Feature vectors are computed for the data to be validated, and subsequences in this data are labeled based on the established model's clusters. UDAVA calculates the deviation metric, which quantifies the extent of deviation of a feature vector and its associated subsequence from the cluster centers in the feature space. This metric gauges how much the feature vector deviates from the behavior patterns represented by the cluster centers.
- (4) **Sequence pruning.** UDAVA enhances its understanding of time series data by identifying continuous data segments, representing uninterrupted sequences of labels over time. However, segments with durations below a specified threshold are considered *noise* and are automatically pruned to improve data quality and label sequence clarity.
- (5) **Event log creation.** This stage generates an event log with human-readable labels from pruned data segments, representing a sequence where events mark segment start and completion. Labels are automatically assigned based on cluster center statistics, but can be overridden by annotated data for improved interpretability. To structure the event log for process mining, UDAVA identifies boundary events that segment the sequence into individual cases, each corresponding to a production cycle. This approach assumes that the industrial process consists of discrete, repetitive cycles, enabling detailed analysis of each cycle.
- (6) **Process discovery and conformance.** Using the event log, a process model can be discovered with existing method. The resulting process model has multiple applications, such as providing insights into overarching trends and patterns at an aggregated level and facilitating conformance checking. Conformance checking involves comparing observed behavior with an expected behavior from a reference process model to detect deviations or anomalies in the production process.

In UDAVA's *semi-supervised mode*, training data is supplemented with annotated data. Manual labels are created by annotating specific sections of reference time series data, representing subprocesses like "Grinding," "Roughing," or "Finishing." A subprocess in this context refers to a distinct phase or step within the overall manufacturing operation, each characterized by its own specific pattern in the sensor data. Label Studio [53], an open-source tool, is employed to streamline the labeling process, generating JSON files for UDAVA input, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 illustrates this labeling process applied to a single production cycle. UDAVA utilizes these manual labels to compute feature vectors and establish cluster centers for each unique label. These cluster centers then serve as initial reference points in the clustering algorithm during Stage 2 (Model creation), aiding in the identification of clusters aligned with the labeled subprocesses.

The data preprocessing stage is applied to both the reference (training) time series data and the operational time series data (to be validated). Feature vectors extracted from the operational data serve as input for Stage 3 (Inference), as shown in Figure 1. The following subsections offer comprehensive insights into each pipeline stage.

4.1 Data Preprocessing (Stage 1)

Raw time series data inherently contains relationships between consecutive time-varying data points. However, clustering such extensive raw time series can be computationally demanding. To

Fig. 2. Example manual labels in Label Studio. The blue line graph shows grinding power data from a roughing process performed by a grinding machine. The x-axis represents time steps; the y-axis indicates grinding power in watts. The text labels above the graph represent seven subprocesses in the production cycle. The colored boxes overlaying the line graph are the labels. They are referred to as “regions”; each region color corresponds to a label.

avoid the computation demand, UDAVA employs feature extraction from time series subsequences, effectively removing the temporal dimension. It utilizes the sliding window technique [21, 36] to create these subsequences, enabling feature extraction from each subsequence and forming feature vectors. These feature vectors capture essential information from the time series data, offering a more manageable and representative representation for subsequent analysis and clustering.

Subsequent to subsequence extraction, a feature vector is generated by aggregating summary statistics. UDAVA employs six fundamental features, each conveying vital insights about the characteristics of these subsequences. These features encompass measures of central tendency such as *mean* and *median*, an indication of change through *gradient*, a measure of data spread in the form of *variance*, a span descriptor known as *range*, and the magnitude of frequency components denoted as *frequency strength*. Table 1 lists the calculations for these features. The range signifies the difference between the minimum and maximum values observed within the subsequence, while the frequency strength is derived from the L2-norm of the **Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)**. To determine the frequency components, the **discrete Fourier transform (DFT)** is applied to derive the frequency domain representation of the subsequence. Subsequently, the magnitude of each frequency component is computed using the Euclidean norm.

Features are given equal weight in clustering and are scaled based on the following equation:

$$f = \frac{f' - \mu}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the feature f' before scaling and f is the scaled feature.

In this pipeline stage, the option exists to incorporate annotated data as supplementary input. These annotations correspond to labels assigned to particular segments within the time series. We compute feature vectors from this annotated data and assign labels to all feature vectors based on

Table 1. List of Engineered Features in UDAVA

Feature name	Mathematical definition
Mean	$\mu = \frac{1}{w} \left(\sum_{i=1}^w x_i \right)$
Median	$m = \begin{cases} x_{\frac{w+1}{2}} & \text{if } w \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{x_{\frac{w}{2}} + x_{\frac{w}{2}+1}}{2} & \text{if } w \text{ is even} \end{cases}$
Range	$r = \max(x) - \min(x)$
Gradient	$\nabla x = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_i - 1}{2d}$
Variance	$v = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^w (x_i - \mu)^2$
Frequency strength	$v = \text{DFT}(w) _2$
Related quantities	Symbol
Rolling window size	w
Time step between each data point	d

the provided annotations. This approach enables the computation of average feature vectors for each assigned label. These averaged feature vectors can subsequently serve as the initial cluster centers when constructing the model in Stage 2 (see Section 4.2). By utilizing these label-associated feature vectors as starting points for clustering, UDAVA can effectively align the clusters with the labeled segments, enhancing the interpretability and coherence of the resulting model.

4.2 Model Creation (Stage 2)

During model creation, UDAVA utilizes unsupervised clustering algorithms to automatically group feature vectors into clusters, revealing hidden patterns in the preprocessed time series data from manufacturing. This stage is crucial for anomaly and deviation detection in future production cycles using the reference model. UDAVA provides flexibility by supporting various clustering algorithms from Scikit-learn [70] in Python, enabling customization to suit IIoT data intricacies.

The effectiveness of clustering in UDAVA is highly dependent on the choice of algorithm, which must align with the characteristics of both the industrial process and the sensor data being analyzed. Key considerations include handling high-dimensional data, accommodating diverse cluster structures, managing noise, and optimizing computational efficiency.

Centroid-based algorithms, such as K-Means, require the number of clusters to be predefined, making them suitable when prior knowledge about distinct process states exists. **Density-based methods**, like DBSCAN and OPTICS, automatically determine the number of clusters and are particularly effective for handling noisy sensor data with irregular distributions.

Mean Shift and Affinity Propagation further enable data-driven cluster count estimation, while **hierarchical clustering** provides deeper insights into process state relationships at the cost of increased computational overhead. Given that clustering performance is highly dataset-dependent, the most effective strategy is empirical experimentation. To support this, UDAVA integrates a configurable clustering framework via Scikit-learn [70], allowing practitioners to select and fine-tune algorithms.

Figure 3 illustrates the clustering process applied to the data points. For the sake of clarity, the plot is constructed using only two features from the multidimensional data space, allowing us to visualize the clusters within a two-dimensional context. The color-coded segments on the plot depict

Fig. 3. Example clusters identified by UDAVA within a two-dimensional feature space, where the x - and y -axes represent two arbitrarily chosen features from the feature vector. Individual observations (or feature vectors) within the dataset are depicted as colored dots, with distinct colors (red, orange, blue, and green) signifying four different clusters as per the model. The diamond markers signify the centers of the clusters. The annotations provide a step-by-step explanation of the calculation of the deviation metric D_l for a particular feature vector, F_l , which is illustrated as a black dot.

how observations are grouped, with similar features assigned to the same color group. Moreover, the diamond-shaped markers conspicuously denote the cluster centers of the four distinct clusters identified in the dataset.

When annotated data is provided during the preprocessing stage, UDAVA utilizes labels to establish initial cluster centers, provided that the chosen clustering algorithm accommodates this feature. Essentially, this integration introduces a semi-supervised learning element into the model creation phase, contributing to the enhancement of interpretability and the precision of the clusters. Consequently, this refinement positively impacts the discernment of process behavior patterns derived from the clustering. It is important to underscore that the model's resilience to real-world fluctuations and deviations from the norm is significantly contingent upon the quality and representativeness of the data employed during this stage. High-quality, comprehensive data plays a fundamental role in the robustness and effectiveness of the resultant model in capturing and characterizing the manufacturing process's nuances and variations.

4.3 Inference (Stage 3)

UDAVA leverages the established cluster model for inference, a task categorizing new, unlabeled data originating from manufacturing processes. The same data preprocessing stage, explained in Section 4.1 and applied to reference data, is used to handle operational data. The reference data is used to train the clustering model employed to label the operational data. Figure 4 illustrates this process: a multicolored line signifies the time-dependent sensor data, with color shifts representing transitions between clusters. Subsequently, the labels assigned to feature vectors are plotted back onto the corresponding subsequences within the temporal dimension.

Fig. 4. Visualization of raw data from the operational dataset (multicolored line) alongside the deviation metric D (black line) for both the reference (upper panel) and operational (lower panel) scenarios. Subsequences are distinguished by the color of the cluster they are assigned to. The peak value of the deviation metric for the reference data is 33.8, while the operational data has a peak of 41.9.

UDAVA detects deviation by computing distances between feature vectors extracted from the operational data and the cluster centers established by the model trained on the reference data. Here, the reference data assumes the role of a benchmark, representing the expected behavior during ideal production cycles. The calculation of the deviation metric commences with the computation of the Euclidean distance between each feature vector within the operational data and every individual cluster center. This computation unfolds within a multidimensional feature space, permitting us to gauge the proximity or divergence of a new observation (feature vector) concerning the predefined cluster centers. It is important to emphasize that these cluster centers are determined based on the average values of the features encapsulated by all feature vectors residing within a specific cluster.

Let the total number of clusters be N with each cluster c indexed by $i \in 1, \dots, N$. The cluster center c_i is as follows:

$$c_i = [\mu_{i,1}, \mu_{i,2}, \dots, \mu_{i,j}, \dots, \mu_{i,M-1}, \mu_{i,M}], \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_{i,j}$ is the mean of the j^{th} feature of all feature vectors in cluster i . The index j runs from 1 to M , where M is the total number of features each feature vector comprises. To calculate the Euclidean distance (denoted as $d_{i,l}$) between each feature vector F_l and cluster center c_i , we use the following equation:

$$d_{i,l} = \sqrt{(f_1 - \mu_{i,1})^2 + \dots + (f_j - \mu_{i,2})^2 + \dots + (f_M - \mu_{i,M})^2}, \quad (3)$$

where f_j is the feature of the given feature vector F_l and $l \in 1, \dots, L$ is the index of the feature vector in the dataset. The sum of distances is computed as follows:

$$D_l = \sum_{i=1}^N d_{i,l}. \quad (4)$$

The deviation metric (D) is a valuable indicator that should be continuously monitored over time. This metric enables the assessment of the degree to which the operational data deviates from the reference data. Such ongoing monitoring is essential for detecting and evaluating any inconsistencies or variations within the manufacturing process.

Our comprehension of deviation hinges on the insight that a feature vector's anomalousness increases as its distance from all cluster centers surpasses that of a specific vector. A single feature vector's distance from a particular cluster center may not conclusively indicate deviation. However, when the vector's distance notably extends beyond that of all cluster centers, it exhibits a potential deviation. Figure 3 depicts the computation of the deviation metric, represented by the black dot, for a given feature vector. Observations positioned at the periphery or beyond the plotted area are likely to signify deviations. The deviation metric never attains a value of zero for any feature vector, whether originating from the reference or operational datasets. Consequently, its interpretation must be contextual, comparing values within the same operational dataset or against the reference dataset. Abrupt spikes or a persistently elevated average of the deviation metric relative to the reference dataset may signal noteworthy deviations or alterations within the operational data.

4.4 Sequence Pruning (Stage 4)

UDAVA post-processes the output of the cluster model to glean additional insights from the data. In pursuit of this objective, it identifies continuous sequences sharing the same label over time, effectively identifying data segments. For example, when there are n consecutive subsequences marked with the **Cluster1** label, UDAVA pinpoints a segment with a duration of $n \cdot w \cdot f$, where w represents the window size of the subsequences and f denotes the sampling frequency. Segments that fall short of a predefined minimum duration (threshold) are considered as *noise* when the expectation is that the time series should exclusively encompass segments meeting or exceeding this minimum duration. UDAVA grants users the flexibility to specify this minimum segment duration. After pruning, the remaining segments are sorted based on their start time in ascending order, and their label and start/end times are saved into an event log (see Section 4.5). By eliminating undesired segments and arranging the retained ones in chronological order based on their commencement times, the resulting data becomes more amenable to visualization and in-depth analysis. UDAVA merges the excessively short segments into one of the neighboring segments, whereby the pruning algorithm identifies the cluster closest to the noisy segment within the feature space. It subsequently presents the results in the time domain for intuitive inspection, particularly when manual labels are integrated, aiding in assessing the pruned segments.

Sequence pruning is crucial in unsupervised learning, like clustering, as it helps eliminate incongruous patterns. This stage is especially important in applications where clear patterns are essential for decision-making, enhancing result reliability and interpretability by refining the output through short segment removal. It commences with identifying all segments within the input labels, subsequently arranging them in ascending order based on their respective lengths. It iteratively assesses the segment lengths, starting from the shortest one. If the current segment length falls below the predefined minimum length, the loop concludes, and the pruned labels are returned. In cases where the segment remains excessively short, the pruning mechanism engages in a series of steps. Firstly,

UDAVA discerns the second closest cluster center for each data point residing within the current short segment. All data points within the same short segment should be assigned to a single cluster label. Hence, UDAVA identifies the optimal candidate within cluster labels for reassignment. To do so, it determines the most frequent second closest cluster center for the data points within the segment. This prevailing second-closest cluster center effectively dictates how the segment is pruned. If the frequently encountered second closest cluster center differs from neighboring segment labels, the current segment splits, with each half merging with adjacent segments. If the most frequent second closest cluster center matches neighboring labels, the entire segment is assigned the matching label. UDAVA repeats this process until no more segments can be eliminated or all meet the required length, reducing noise for more robust output.

Figure 5 illustrates the pruning stage with an example. In the upper graph (1), a segment of the time series is displayed before undergoing pruning. The middle one (2) depicts a snapshot of the time series during pruning. Here, the grey segment is too short, and most data points in this one exhibit the blue cluster as the second closest cluster center within the feature space, leading to its merger with the blue segment. The lower graph (3) depicts the pruned time series, with the red segment having neither the yellow nor purple cluster as the second closest cluster center. The red

Fig. 5. Pruning short segments in the inference output (time series before, during, and after pruning).

segment is divided into two and merged with adjacent ones. The blue segment, below the minimum length, is similarly divided and distributed between the purple and brown ones.

4.5 Event Log Creation (Stage 5)

After sequence pruning, we obtain a sequence of segments with start and end timestamps. UDAVA leverages this sequence to construct an event log, a resource for visualizing and examining production cycles (verifying the expected duration and order of activities in operational process cycles). Events record each segment's start and end times with their associated labels. The event log generation iteratively extracts labels and the start and completion timestamps from each segment. This is utilized to construct two events for each segment: one for the start time and one for the completion time. This sequence is represented in the first three columns in Table 2. The *status* column denotes whether the event signals the start or completion. Each event corresponds to label occurrences in the cluster model, aiding in scrutinizing and validating expected activity durations and sequences (e.g., *Rotating*, *Roughing*, *Dressing*, and *Finishing*) in the production process (see Section 4.6).

The process discovery and conformance stage relies on an event log, which should include event labels (denoting activities) and timestamps for sequencing. While timestamps inherently provide sequence information, process mining requires event grouping into cases, as explained in Section 4.1. The fourth column in Table 2 illustrates this structuring, where each event carries a unique case identifier. In our context, a case represents a single production cycle instance. Thus, Table 2 distinguishes two machining process instances based on distinct activity sets identified by UDAVA. However, these case identifiers need to be identified by UDAVA.

Diverging from approaches designed for handling the correlation of events in generic business processes [10, 25], we can leverage two key factors: (1) domain knowledge about the production process and (2) the expectation of only one active case at any given moment. With the constraint that only a single case can be active, we can divide the event sequence using predefined *start*, *end*, or *idle* segments. These boundary segments are often sourced from process documentation or domain expertise. For instance, in the machining process in Figure 2, an idle state occurs during production where the grinding machine operates a sufficiently long time without material (*Rotating*), signifying both the start and end segments of a production cycle. We can now use such an *idle* segment to subdivide the event log into cases by increasing the case identifier each time such an event occurs.

UDAVA supports defining a reference collection of boundary segments alongside a time threshold denoting the minimum required duration for a segment to qualify as a valid boundary segment. This feature prevents the initiation of new process cases by brief, transient segments unless they have already been pruned in Stage 4 (see Section 4.4). Determining an appropriate threshold necessitates parameter adjustment tailored to the specific use case. As already indicated, for Table 2, we could specify that *Rotating* with a minimum duration is an *idle* segment. Then, given the event sequence

Table 2. An Example Event Sequence UDAVA Obtains

Timestamp	Label	Status	Case
2022-05-30T14:09:00	Rotating	Started	A
2022-05-30T14:09:08	Rotating	Completed	A
2022-05-30T14:09:08	Roughing	Started	A
2022-05-30T14:09:13	Roughing	Completed	A
2022-05-30T14:09:13	Dressing	Started	A
2022-05-30T14:09:16	Dressing	Completed	A
2022-05-30T14:09:16	Rotating	Started	A
2022-05-30T14:09:17	Rotating	Completed	A
2022-05-30T14:09:17	Finishing	Started	A
2022-05-30T14:09:20	Finishing	Completed	A
2022-05-30T14:09:20	Rotating	Started	B
2022-05-30T14:09:35	Rotating	Completed	B
2022-05-30T14:09:35	Roughing	Started	B
2022-05-30T14:09:40	Roughing	Completed	B
2022-05-30T14:09:40	Finishing	Started	B
2022-05-30T14:09:46	Finishing	Completed	B

The first three columns (Timestamp, Label, and Status) can be directly obtained from the output of UDAVA's clustering step. The fourth column (Case) needs to be inferred based on process knowledge or discovered based on detecting a repetitive pattern.

Fig. 6. DFG model discovered from the event log excerpt shown in Table 2. The *Start* and *End* nodes are added depicting the boundaries of the process. Both the transition frequency and the mean waiting and processing times are projected onto the edges and nodes in the graph. The color scale used for the nodes indicate the average processing time.

of $\langle Rot + S, Rot + C, Rou + S, Rou + C, Dres + S, Dres + C, Rot + S, Rot + C, Fin + S, Fin + C, Rot + S, Rot + C, Rou + S, Rou + C, Fin + S, Fin + C \rangle$, we obtain two cases denoted by *A* and *B* in column *case*. The event log can be subjected to in-depth analysis, facilitating the detection of patterns or anomalies within the production process (see Section 4.6).

4.6 Process Discovery and Conformance (Stage 6)

Process discovery takes an event log (e.g., the one in Table 2) and derives a process model as a compact representation of the observed sequences. Conformance checking takes a discovered or manually defined process model and pinpoints the deviations between the model and an event log.

Process Discovery. Process models delineate the sequential ordering of activities (in our case, clustered segments) within a process over an extended timeframe. These models not only convey sequential arrangements but also highlight activity conflicts. Various notations exist for process models generated by state-of-the-art process discovery methods. Petri nets are frequently employed in academic contexts since they can succinctly represent concurrent behavior, where multiple activities can simultaneously occur or in arbitrary order. However, our scenario involves segments generated from a single machine, representing sequential steps within a production process devoid of parallel activities. For instance, a grinding machine may process multiple pieces simultaneously but can only engage in either *Dressing* or *Roughing* at any moment. Therefore, we opt for the **Directly-follows Graph (DFG)** [54] as a suitable process model for capturing the essence of our target processes. A DFG model is a directed graph representing the observed, directly following relations in the event log. A directed edge connecting two nodes (*A* and *B*), denoting activities from the event log, signifies that step *B* is directly observed to follow the completion of step *A*. In addition to visualizing binary relationships between activities, we incorporate metrics such as occurrence frequency and inter-step duration onto the edges. Furthermore, we annotate the nodes with the total occurrence frequency of steps and their mean processing times. We employ the techniques outlined by Leemans et al. [54] to construct DFGs that can be refined to exclude rare behaviors while preserving coherent semantics, rendering them apt for analysis and conformance checking. For visualization, we make use of the bupaR framework [50].

Figure 6 displays the DFG model derived from the event log excerpt in Table 2. The green *Start* and red *End* nodes are included to mark the process instance boundaries. The edges are proportionally scaled based on the observed frequency of each relation. Figure 6 presents two instances where the

Fig. 7. A Petri net encoding the set of expected sequences for the grinding process, which may be different from the discovered process. We use the transitions (rectangles) of the Petri net to indicate the occurrence of a certain activity (e.g., *Dressing*). The places (circles) of the Petri net indicate the pre- and post-conditions of the activity. For an activity to occur a token (black dot) needs to be in all of its input places and when it is performed tokens are put on all of its output places. The overall process behavior is specified by taking all possible runs from the initial state (token in the initial place) to a deadlock state (no further execution is possible). A special unobservable activity *tau* is used to model the option to skip a certain activity.

process began with *Rotating*. The event log has no time gap between activities, as the segments transition seamlessly without pruned short-lived activities, resulting in a waiting time of 0 seconds. Note that cycles in the process can be represented as evident in Figure 6 through the edge back from *Dressing* to *Rotating*, which happened once in the example data.

Conformance Checking. The DFG model offers valuable insights into the repetitive behavior identified through the UDAVA clustering output. In scenarios characterized by highly structured and sequential production processes, we anticipate that most cases will adhere to a consistent sequence with comparable processing and inter-step waiting times. The DFG model is an effective tool for detecting and analyzing deviations, such as the absence of a step or the occurrence of two steps in the wrong order, when deviations from the expected behavior are minimal.

When numerous deviations exist or when no predominant sequence is followed, the DFG model can become cluttered with several edges connecting nodes. In such cases, we can employ conformance checking, i.e., a process mining task that compares observed behavior to a predefined process description [19]. As part of UDAVA an existing process description can be manually modeled as a process model expressed in Petri net notation. Subsequently, UDAVA computes an alignment between this Petri net and the event log [19, 54]. This alignment provides a mapping between all the sequences described by the model and observed sequences in the event log. For instance, if we consider the Petri net shown in Figure 7 and the observed input sequence $\langle Rot, Rough, Fin \rangle$, the model prescribes that the activity *Dressing* needs to be either after or before *Roughing* but cannot be skipped. The alignment process matches activities in the observed sequence with specific execution sequences (runs) defined by the model.

Table 3 indicates such a possible alignment for our example event sequence. Each row pairs an observed activity from the event sequence with the corresponding activity observed in the execution of the Petri net. Discrepancies are denoted with the skip symbol \gg indicating either an invalid event observation (log move only) or a missing activity according to the model (model move only). UDAVA employs the standard conformance-checking approach based on an A^* search [19] offering an optimal alignment, wherein a search yields the alignment with the minimum number of mismatches. By aligning each sequence in the event log with a reference process model, deviations can be scrutinized at a granular level, and frequent mismatches can be visualized using color scales applied to the provided reference DFG model.

Table 3. A Possible Alignment between the Input Sequence $\langle Rot, Rou, Fin \rangle$ and the Petri Net in Figure 7

Log move	Model move
Rotating	Rotating
Roughing	Roughing
\gg	Dressing
Finishing	Finishing

5 Evaluation

We investigate, based on three main datasets, the following RQs:

- **RQ1.** *To what extent can UDAVA discover behavior patterns in IIoT sensor data for a reference production cycle?* The goal of this RQ is to assess UDAVA’s capability to identify behavior patterns within IIoT sensor data that correspond to a reference production cycle.
- **RQ2.** *Does comparing process behavior patterns reveal process shifts and drifts in subsequent production cycles?* This RQ aims to determine if analyzing process behavior patterns can effectively identify process shifts and drifts in subsequent production cycles, thereby evaluating UDAVA’s capability to detect deviations in industrial processes.
- **RQ3.** *To what extent can UDAVA reveal and be used to analyze the high-level repetitive process behavior on an aggregate level of several production cycles?* This question aims to evaluate UDAVA’s ability to uncover and analyze repetitive process behavior across multiple production cycles, providing insights into aggregated patterns and trends in industrial operations.

5.1 Experiment Design

Datasets. We assessed UDAVA on three main datasets: power measurements from the NOVA9 grinding machine, power measurements from the NOVA10 grinding machine, and accelerometer data from an aerospace industry broaching machine. Each main dataset has two sub-datasets (e.g., NOVA9 dataset has NOVA9-10Hz and NOVA9-1Hz datasets), resulting in **six datasets in total**. Table 4 gives an overview of the datasets.

NOVA9. The NOVA9 dataset comprises sensor data from the Fersa NOVA9 grinding machine, dedicated to grinding inner bearing rings [32], with measurements of grinding power (in watts, W) and accelerometer readings (in meters per second squared, m/s²). It includes two datasets: NOVA9-10Hz, sampled on June 8th, 2021, at 25,600 Hz, downsampled to 10 Hz for UDAVA processing, utilizing 5,590 data samples from the production of 14 parts for model creation in RQ1, and NOVA9-1Hz, gathered between October 18th, 2023, and January 11th, 2024, at 1 Hz, used for RQ2 evaluation on drifts and shifts. Both datasets were used for RQ3.

NOVA10. The NOVA10 dataset includes sensor data from the Fersa NOVA10 grinding machine, tailored for grinding inner bearing ring

flanges [32], featuring measurements of grinding power (kW) and accelerometer readings (m/s²). Exclusive utilization of grinding power data from a wattmeter was employed for this study. Like the NOVA9 scenario, two datasets were utilized with different sampling frequencies: NOVA10-10Hz, sampled on May 21st, 2021, at 16,384 Hz, resampled to 10 Hz for computational efficiency, utilizing 5,859 data samples for RQ1 model creation, and NOVA10-1Hz, collected between October 15th, 2023, and January 26th, 2024, at 1 Hz, utilized for RQ2 evaluation. Both datasets were used for RQ3.

Aerospace. The Aerospace dataset, gathered on May 24th, 2021, documents the broaching process on turbine discs for jet engines. Three broaching tools executed the operation, removing material at a lift velocity of 19 meters per minute and a 15-degree slot angle. It includes data from

Table 4. Statistics of the Datasets

Dataset	CPS	# of Samples
NOVA9-10Hz	Grinding machine	5590
NOVA9-1Hz	Grinding machine	4937139
NOVA10-10Hz	Grinding machine	5859
NOVA10-1Hz	Grinding machine	6544230
Aerospace-Reference	Broaching machine	954496
Aerospace-Full	Broaching machine	11515566

Table 5. Configuration Parameters Used in the Experiments

Dataset	Variable	Clustering algorithm	# of Cluste.	Wind. Size	Thresh. for pruning
NOVA9-10Hz	Grinding power	Mini-batch KMeans	6	10	1
NOVA9-1Hz	Grinding power	Mini-batch KMeans	6	3	1
NOVA10-10Hz	Grinding power	Mini-batch KMeans	7	5	1
NOVA10-1Hz	Grinding power	Mini-batch KMeans	7	3	1
Aerospace-Reference	Accelerometer z-axis	Mini-batch KMeans	3	2,000	3
Aerospace-Full	Accelerometer z-axis	Mini-batch KMeans	3	2,000	3

two accelerometers sampled at approximately 7.8125 milliseconds, a data logger at four millisecond intervals, and tool wear measurements via an optical microscope. Only the z-axis accelerometer data was used for UDAVA input, focusing on dynamic broaching aspects. The dataset covers 50 consecutive slots, from slot 11 to 60, split into Aerospace-Reference (broaching the first four slots for RQ1 model creation) and Aerospace-Full (all 50 slots).

Experimental Setup. We optimized UDAVA’s configuration parameters through manual trial-and-error, tailoring them for each dataset based on domain expertise and prior experience with similar industrial datasets (see Table 5). Specifically, we assessed different window sizes and clustering algorithms and examined their impact on clustering performance, ensuring that the extracted features effectively captured the key transitions and phases of the production cycles without excessive fragmentation or loss of detail. Mini-batch KMeans proved the most effective clustering algorithm, with the window size (w) optimized for each dataset based on sampling frequency. The number of clusters was determined based on known subprocesses, while boundary events in event log creation were guided by domain expertise: *Spark out* for NOVA9, *Finishing* directly followed by *Finishing Spark Out* for NOVA10, and *Broaching* for the Aerospace dataset. The minimum duration threshold for sequence pruning was also decided through manual trial-and-error. For the NOVA9 and NOVA10 datasets, no sequence pruning was needed due to little noise in the labelling, but for the Aerospace dataset we employed a threshold of 3, meaning that any segments consisting of less than 3 subsequences with the same label will be pruned.

5.2 Results

This section discusses the results of our case studies, addressing, in turn, each of the RQs.

RQ1: To what Extent Can UDAVA Discover Behavior Patterns in IIoT Sensor Data for a Reference Production Cycle? To address RQ1, we compared UDAVA’s event log with the expected outcome through: (a) computing an event log score (S) based on expected event order and duration, (b) assessing precision and recall against manual labels for the entire time series, and (c) evaluating UDAVA’s ability to identify start and completion timestamps of behavior patterns.

The initial assessment involved computing an event log score (S) based on expected label order and duration ranges. Hits represented correct occurrences, while misses indicated discrepancies. The event log score (S) was computed using the formula (number of hits/(number of hits + number of misses)), ranging from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating a perfect match and 0 indicating none. The event log score functions as a form of accuracy score for the label order and duration ranges. Table 6 lists the predefined expectations.

Table 7 displays the event log scores, including scores for event duration (S_d) and event sequence (S_n). Scores were 0.67 and 0.66 in NOVA9-10Hz and Aerospace-Reference, respectively, while NOVA10-10Hz scored 0.45. In the

Table 6. Expected Durations for Labels Are Determined from Observed Durations in Reference Data for Each Dataset

Dataset	Label	Expected duration range (seconds)
NOVA9	Rotating grinding wheel	0-10,000
	Rotating grinding wheel + coolant	1-3
	Roughing	4-7
	Semifinishing	8-12
	Finishing	2-4
	Sparkout	1-3
NOVA10	Rotating grinding wheel	0-10,000
	Rotating grinding wheel + coolant	3-7
	Roughing	2-8
	Roughing spark out	1-5
	Dressing operation	3-7
	Finishing	3-10
Aerospace	Finishing spark out	2-8
	Broaching	1-4
	Lift moving	1-8
	No action	1-8

The “Rotating grinding wheel” label has a wide expected duration range, accounting for extended inactive periods between production cycles recorded over multiple days. The order of labels is inferred from Figures 8, 9, and 10.

Aerospace case, the model showed better event duration matching ($S_d = 0.74$) than event sequence matching ($S_n = 0.58$). We observed no significant difference in other cases. Anomalies were absent in the reference data, indicating expected high event log scores if UDAVA successfully detects subprocesses matching the expectations.

The event log score, while simple, focuses mainly on matching subsequent labels to expected ones, lacking the ability to detect alignment beyond two consecutive segments. While limited as a standalone metric, it supports trend identification, particularly in RQ2. Its value lies in defining process expectations without extensive manual labeling. We complemented this with manual labeling to assess *precision*, *recall*, and overall *accuracy*, akin to evaluating the categorization ability of a classifier. *Precision* measures true positives in all positive predictions, *recall* identifies actual positives correctly, and *accuracy* denotes true results in the population.

Evaluating the event log’s accuracy offers limited insights into UDAVA’s performance, as it prioritizes assigning correct labels to each timestamp, which may not be the primary concern in unsupervised segmentation without ground truth labels. Given the significance of specific subprocesses like machining operations in manufacturing processes, we further assessed UDAVA’s capability to identify the start and end points of these key processes, e.g., broaching, milling, and grinding, as a crucial comparison measure.

In the NOVA9 dataset, UDAVA showed notable precision and recall in identifying machining segments, as seen in Table 8. Notably, it exhibited high precision for “Rotating grinding wheel” (86.96%) and “Rotating grinding wheel + coolant” (95.00%), indicating its ability to identify these segments accurately. However, recall for “Roughing” (27.01%) suggests room for improvement in capturing all instances of certain segments. Nonetheless, the overall accuracy was robust at 72.54%, demonstrating the effectiveness of UDAVA in pattern recognition. Figure 8 visually compares actual and detected labels, showcasing the performance of UDAVA in identifying machining segments in the NOVA9 dataset.

Temporal accuracy, a pivotal facet of the performance of UDAVA, underwent assessment by computing the average absolute error in detecting the start and completion times of the “Roughing” machining segment. Table 9 displays the outcomes, revealing a negligible average error for the start time (0.34 seconds),

Table 7. Event Log Scores, Including the Total Score (S), the Score (S_d) When Only Considering the Expected Duration, and the Score (S_n) When Only Considering the Expected Next Event

Dataset	S	S_d	S_n
NOVA9-10Hz	0.67	0.67	0.66
NOVA10-10Hz	0.45	0.46	0.44
Aerospace-Reference	0.66	0.58	0.74

Table 8. Precision, Recall and Overall Accuracy of Pattern Discovery for the NOVA9 Dataset

Label	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Rotating grinding wheel	86.96	94.14
Rotating grinding wheel + coolant	95.00	53.52
Roughing	99.09	27.01
Semifinishing	63.58	73.41
Finishing	33.05	58.21
Spark out	54.77	60.55
Overall accuracy (%)	72.54	

Fig. 8. True and discovered labels for the NOVA9 dataset.

Table 9. Average Absolute Error for Identification of Point in Time for Start and Completion of Machining Segments

Dataset	Machining Segment	Average error for start(s)	Average error for end(s)
NOVA9-10Hz	Roughing	0.34	3.88
NOVA10-10Hz	Roughing	2.47	1.23
Aerospace-Reference	Broaching	0.16	0.03

signifying precise identification of this segment’s start. A larger average error for the completion time (3.88 seconds) implies potential discrepancies in pinpointing the end of the “Roughing” segment, highlighting an area for future refinement.

In the NOVA10 dataset, UDAVA showed varied precision and recall across machining segments (see Table 10). Notably, it demonstrates moderate precision for “Rotating grinding wheel” (50.06%) and higher precision for “Rotating grinding wheel + coolant” (78.29%), alongside exceptional recall for “Rotating grinding wheel” (95.65%). Conversely, the “Roughing” segment exhibits lower precision (58.88%) and recall (41.59%), indicating areas for improvement in pattern recognition. Interestingly, “Roughing spark out” achieves perfect precision (100.00%) but only 20.92% recall, suggesting occasional oversight of relevant instances. Figure 9 visually compares actual and detected labels in the NOVA10 dataset.

The overall accuracy for NOVA10 is 60.71%, indicating the model’s ability to classify grinding process segments. However, this underscores potential performance enhancement, particularly in segments with low recall. Varied precision and recall across segments reveal nuanced challenges. High precision but low recall of segments like “Roughing spark out” suggest an overly conservative model, while lower precision and recall of segments like “Roughing” indicate the need for improved capturing of process complexity.

For the NOVA10 dataset, we assessed the temporal precision of UDAVA in segment detection. Table 9 shows an average absolute error of 2.47 seconds for initiating the “Roughing” segment, indicating moderate precision compared to NOVA9. Conversely, completion detection had an average error of 1.23 seconds, demonstrating higher accuracy. This result underscores the need to improve the detection of the segment start while preserving or enhancing completion precision for effective industrial process analysis and optimization.

In the Aerospace dataset, we applied UDAVA with a window size of 2,000 samples and the mini-batch KMeans algorithm. Figure 10 illustrates the actual and discovered labels, while Table 11 shows pattern discovery accuracy overall and for specific sub-processes. UDAVA excelled in identifying and labeling the broaching subprocess, with 98.58% precision and 91.15% recall. However, distinguishing

Table 10. Accuracy of Pattern Discovery for the NOVA10 Dataset

Label	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Rotating grinding wheel	50.06	95.65
Rotating grinding wheel + coolant	78.29	80.88
Roughing	58.88	41.59
Roughing spark out	100.00	20.92
Dressing operation	–	–
Finishing	80.66	64.04
Finishing spark out	45.30	52.22
Overall accuracy (%)	60.71	

Fig. 9. True and discovered labels for the NOVA10 dataset.

Fig. 10. True and discovered labels for the Aerospace dataset.

Table 11. Accuracy of Pattern Discovery in the Aerospace Dataset

Label	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Broaching	98.58	91.15
Lift moving	76.35	56.20
No action	67.62	84.84
Overall accuracy (%)	75.11	

Fig. 11. Sensor data from the NOVA9-1Hz dataset processed with UDAVA, comparing a slot with normal behavior against detected anomalies.

between “No action” and “Lift moving” posed challenges, resulting in lower performance scores for these subprocesses. Overall, the Aerospace dataset achieved 75.11% accuracy.

UDAVA detected the machining segments in the Aerospace dataset, as shown in Table 9. The average error for segment initiation was merely 0.16 seconds, with completion error even lower at 0.03 seconds. This accuracy is aided by the distinct acceleration amplitudes observed during “Broaching” compared to “No action” and “Lift moving,” as illustrated in Figure 10.

RQ1 Conclusion. UDAVA displayed good precision and recall in identifying crucial machining segments accurately. Yet, challenges surfaced, notably in the varying precision and recall across segments. Additionally, its accuracy in pinpointing segments’ start and end varied, indicating areas for refinement. Overall, UDAVA demonstrated promise in industrial process pattern recognition, though enhancements are warranted in specific contexts.

RQ2: Does Comparing Process Behavior Patterns Reveal Process Shifts and Drifts in Subsequent Production Cycles? To address RQ2, we compared process behavior patterns across different periods, analyzing metrics such as event log scores and deviation metrics to detect changes in the production process. For the NOVA9 case, we utilized the NOVA9-1Hz dataset to assess deviation metrics and event log scores over a 20-day timeframe. Due to the lower 1 Hz sampling frequency, we employed a new UDAVA model with a reduced window size (refer to Table 5). Across this period, identical workpieces were manufactured, but during the latter 10 days (*period B*), roughing process stock removal notably decreased compared to the initial ten days (*period A*). Our focus was on identifying whether UDAVA could detect this behavioral change.

Figure 11 illustrates sensor data labeled with UDAVA for (a) period A (Nov 2nd) and (b) period B (Nov 15th). Notably, the maximum grinding power decreases from around 15 kW to below 8 kW between Nov 2nd and Nov 15th. Consequently, the roughing (brown) and semi-finishing segments (yellow) are consistently unrecognized. Figure 12(a) depicts the changes in the deviation metric and event log score during these periods. As expected, the event log score consistently decreases, indicating a behavioral change. The deviation metric also significantly decreases from period A to period B, detecting deviations from a baseline. The absence of data points representing the “Roughing” and “Semi-finishing” segments due to decreased power levels contributes to the lower deviation metric. Figure 13 displays the data points from Figure 11 in a two-dimensional feature space alongside cluster centers. Data points for Nov 15th cluster more compactly around the centers, explaining the lower deviation metric, which aids in detecting a shift in the production process.

The NOVA10 dataset was utilized akin to NOVA9, comparing the event log score and deviation metric in periods A and B. Figure 12(b) demonstrates a contrasting trend compared to the NOVA9 case: the event log score remains stable in period A but steadily increases in period B. The deviation

Fig. 12. Deviation metric and event log score over time for the three datasets.

Fig. 13. Visualizing the data points from Figure 11 in two dimensions of the feature space. The diamond markers indicate cluster centers.

metric displays fluctuations but exhibits a clear increase in period B. These metric changes indicate the detection of a production process shift, though not as pronounced as in the NOVA9 case.

To assess UDAVA with the aerospace dataset, we tracked the deviation metric and event log score across consecutive broaching cycles. Figure 12(c) displays the maximum deviation metric and event log score for each slot, with the deviation metric represented on a logarithmic scale to accommodate extreme values without obscuring normal behavior details. While the deviation metric typically remains well below 100, Table 12 lists instances with significantly higher values. Sensor data visualization in Figure 14 illustrates abnormal behavior during affected slots compared to a typical broaching cycle. Slot 16 exhibits notably large deviations, with sensor values over ten times the usual amount, reflected in a high deviation metric of 44,442. Slots 17, 18, and 31 show less extreme behavior with lower deviation metric values. The event log score displays minor fluctuations without a trend, suggesting no significant deviations

Table 12. Deviation for Slots with a Metric of Magnitude 10^2 or Higher, Indicating a Notable Increase from the Baseline

Slot Number	Deviation Metric
16	44442
17	2633
18	734
31	195

Fig. 14. Sensor data from the Aerospace-Full dataset processed with UDAVA, comparing a slot with normal behavior against some of the detected anomalies.

in expected segment order and duration. This indicates the capability of UDAVA to detect deviations from normal behavior in the aerospace dataset.

RQ2 Conclusion. Comparing process behaviors revealed notable metric variations across periods. In NOVA9 and NOVA10 cases, distinct trends in event log scores and deviation metrics signaled production process changes. Likewise, in the aerospace case, UDAVA reliably spotted deviations during broaching cycles, highlighting its efficacy in detecting process shifts for optimization and quality control. These findings underscore the efficacy of UDAVA in detecting process deviations, offering valuable insights for process optimization and quality control.

RQ3: To what Extent Can UDAVA Reveal and be used to Analyze the High-level Repetitive Process Behavior on an Aggregate Level of Several Production Cycles? To respond to RQ3, we examined the aggregated process behavior extracted from the event logs generated by all events within the datasets. Initially, we focused on the event logs derived from the NOVA9 and NOVA10 datasets featuring a high sampling frequency of 10 Hz, encompassing approximately 30 grinding cycles. Utilizing a bar plot, we visually represent the event log, depicting the duration of activities across all cases as colored bars along the x -axis (the number of cases was depicted on the y -axis). Figures 15 and 16 provide these visualizations for the NOVA9 and NOVA10 datasets, respectively. In addition, Figure 17 gives the bar plot showing the event log obtained for the aerospace dataset.

UDAVA generally exhibits consistent detection of activities with expected durations, indicating reliable identification of key boundary activities such as “Finishing” (teal) and “Finishing Spark Out” (orange). Furthermore, it effectively captures longer breaks between production cycles in the

Fig. 15. Bar plot displaying the complete event log derived from the NOVA9-10Hz dataset, with each case represented on a separate row (y-axis) and the duration of activities indicated by colored bars. Short cases suggest erroneous detection of the *Spark Out* activity (used for partitioning the event log).

Fig. 16. Bar plot displaying the complete event log from the NOVA10-10Hz dataset. Excluding incomplete cases at the dataset’s beginning and end, UDAVA reveals a regular and repetitive process.

Fig. 17. Bar plot showing the complete event log obtained for the Aerospace dataset.

Fig. 18. Directly-follows model found for 26 out of the original 29 cases in the NOVA9-10Hz dataset.

NOVA9 dataset. However, as highlighted in RQ1, precision issues persist in detecting boundary activities, leading to brief erroneous cases. In NOVA10, variations in activity durations across production cycles are apparent, with instances where the “Finishing” activity (light green) is absent in Figure 16. Please note that the visualization of process cases facilitates such insights.

We discovered a directly-follows model for both datasets, as depicted in Figure 18 for NOVA9-10Hz and Figure 19 for NOVA10-10Hz. Some paths within the model were rarely followed. To streamline the model and concentrate on the repetitive behavior, we eliminated cases from the

Fig. 19. Directly-follows model identified for all 15 out of the original 16 cases in the NOVA10-10Hz dataset.

Fig. 20. Conformance diagnostics overlaid on a manually designed Petri net reveal missing events. Numbers denote total transition occurrences, while colors indicate the frequency of unmatched events.

event log where a path was traversed only once. In NOVA10, the removed cases corresponded to very short sequences attributed to the erroneous detection of boundary activities. Excluding unreasonably short sequences could be considered a mitigation strategy to address this issue.

In the NOVA9-10Hz dataset (Figure 18), 14 cases conclude directly with “Spark Out” after “Rotating Grinding Wheel,” aligning with the brief, erroneous cases highlighted in Figure 15. In the remaining cases, “Rotating Grinding Wheel” may alternate with “Coolant” addition, followed by “Roughing” and multiple instances of “Semifinishing” and “Finishing” activities. This sequence mirrors the anticipated order of activities in the production process. However, certain activities (“Finishing” and “Semifinishing”) appear excessively repeated, consistent with observations in Figure 8.

In the NOVA10-10Hz dataset (Figure 19), the identified process follows the expected sequence of “Rotating,” “Roughing,” and “Roughing Spark Out.” However, “Dressing Operation” and “Finishing Spark Out” are mistakenly identified multiple times in a cycle, whereas they should only occur once per cycle. The “Rotating” and “Rotating + Coolant” activities also appear more frequently than anticipated (> 15 times), yet this is consistent within the context of the grinding operations. Detecting such a recurring pattern aids in diagnosing UDAVA and would be challenging to discern without process mining visualization.

We assessed the alignment between the event log detected during the NOVA10 machine’s grinding process and the predefined process model. Figure 20 illustrates the conformance diagnostics of the NOVA10-10Hz dataset against a Petri net model of the NOVA10 process, manually constructed based on domain knowledge. This model allows for variability of the “Dressing Operation,” since the domain expert noted that may occur several times and at different phases. Specifically, within the NOVA10-10Hz dataset, the “Dressing Operation” precedes “Roughing” in 14 instances. The conformance diagnostics affirm that the detected events by UDAVA generally align with the anticipated process flow.

To assess UDAVA’s efficacy in capturing recurrent process behaviors over extended periods, we analyzed DFGs derived from larger datasets at a lower sampling rate (NOVA9-1Hz and NOVA10-1Hz). Focusing on two specific periods (A and B), as previously delineated in Figure 13 for RQ2, we examined the process models depicted in Figures 21 (NOVA 9) and 22 (NOVA 10) for these intervals. These models aggregate process behaviors, showing average activity times across thousands of cases and up to 246,000 events. For this analysis, we refined the event log from UDAVA’s Stage

(a) 1st November until 11th November with 11 503 cases and 246 932 events.

(b) 11st November until 21th November with 14 947 cases and 268 696 events.

Fig. 21. Directly-follows models identified for two consecutive periods in the larger NOVA9-1Hz dataset, filtered to ensure all paths are traversed for at least 10 times.

5 (see Figure 1) to include only cases with throughput times under 2 minutes and activities with processing times below 1 minute, aiming to concentrate on periods of active machine production despite longer potential durations for states, such as “Rotating Grinding Wheel.”

In the NOVA9-1Hz dataset (see Figure 21), most cases conform to the expected sequence, as shown by the thick blue edges in the directly-follows model. Nonetheless, consistent with findings for RQ2, period B exhibits an increased divergence from the expected process flow, with “Finishing” frequently detected immediately after “Rotating Grinding Wheel + Coolant;” and “Roughing” less often observed than in period A. The interest in the variability of completion times for grinding activities is highlighted by the observed differences in average durations for “Semifinishing” and “Finishing” between periods A and B, likely attributable to varying process parameters. Additionally, a shift in the average duration for “Rotating Grinding Wheel” is observed, possibly due to a rise in

(a) 1st November until 11th November with 886 cases and 13 028 events.

(b) 11st November until 21th November with 1 926 cases and 30 052 events.

Fig. 22. Directly-follows models identified for consecutive periods in the larger NOVA10-1Hz dataset, filtered to ensure all paths are traversed at least 10 times.

cases (1,108 compared to 45) where “Rotating Grinding Wheel” is swiftly succeeded by “Spark Out,” indicating non-productive instances (not actual production).

In the NOVA10-1Hz dataset (see Figure 22), fewer cases meet the limits of throughput and processing times. By capping processing time at 2 minutes, we excluded activities labeled “Rotating Grinding Wheel” (without coolant) from the analysis. Notably, commencing almost all process executions with a “Dressing Operation” suggests challenges in recognizing brief “Rotating Grinding

Fig. 23. Directly-follows model discovered for the Aerospace dataset.

Wheel” operations at the process onset. This observation underscores the previously mentioned concern regarding the low event log score highlighted in RQ2.

In the Aerospace dataset (see Figure 23), we identified a process flow encompassing all 84 recorded cases, characterized by its simplicity with only three distinct activities. The challenge of differentiating between “No action” and “Lift moving,” as highlighted in RQ1, is evident in the process flow, where these activities alternate before the detection of “Broaching.”

RQ3 Conclusion. Aggregating process behaviors into an event log and applying process mining techniques provided enhanced insights into UDAVA’s performance over extended periods, facilitating a more nuanced characterization of metric variations. For datasets exhibiting high accuracy (e.g., NOVA 9), UDAVA’s process mining capability enabled the analysis of numerous process flows simultaneously, offering critical insights that could be overlooked by solely focusing on deviation metrics (RQ2) or brief sampled durations (RQ1).

5.3 Threats to Validity

5.3.1 Internal Validity. We systematically addressed internal validity threats in our evaluation. Initially, we recognized that manually adjusting algorithm parameters, such as window size and clustering, could introduce bias. To mitigate this risk, we employed sensitivity analysis and cross-validation techniques. Furthermore, we plan to integrate an automated configuration approach based on Bayesian optimization and metamorphic testing (as proposed in [84]) to find optimal parameters dynamically. However, defining metamorphic relations for UDAVA and incorporating this automation is beyond the scope of this article and will be addressed in a future study.

Moreover, we documented our data preprocessing methods and reasoning to mitigate potential impacts on results from preprocessing steps like data resampling, ensuring transparency throughout the data transformation process. We also acknowledged the significance of data volume in influencing model performance, noting that larger datasets may lead to more robust outcomes, and delved into the implications of dataset size on the performance of UDAVA. Additionally, to enhance reproducibility, UDAVA, apart from the process mining components, is fully open-source and can be accessed via its GitHub repository (<https://sintef-9012.github.io/Udava/>). This repository also includes a screen cast demonstrating how to use UDAVA.

5.3.2 External Validity. Our study faces a primary external threat concerning generalizability, typical in industrial case studies, which we addressed by considering various external validity concerns in our evaluation. Concerning dataset characteristics, while we selected diverse datasets to bolster generalizability, the applicability of UDAVA across other domains may vary, necessitating further exploration. Moreover, industrial processes undergo continuous evolution, impacting the performance of UDAVA over time; thus, researchers should assess how UDAVA adapts to evolving processes. Additionally, the performance may be influenced by the diverse sensor types and configurations in industrial settings, warranting investigation into its compatibility with various sensor characteristics. Lastly, while our evaluation focused on experimental contexts, deploying UDAVA

in real-world industrial settings may introduce external validity concerns related to hardware limitations, data transmission, and scalability, highlighting the need for future research to address these practical challenges.

5.3.3 Construct Validity. We tackled several construct validity threats in our evaluation. Concerning evaluation metrics, we diversified our metrics, including precision, recall, and accuracy, alongside additional measures like event log score. Additionally, to address the challenge of manual labeling, we employed multiple experts and inter-rater reliability assessments to enhance consistency. Moreover, we ensured that the effectiveness of UDAVA aligns with the specific constructs or behavior patterns targeted within industrial sensor data by validating their relevance through domain expertise and expert consultations.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, this article has presented UDAVA, an unsupervised ML pipeline tailored for sensor data validation in the IIoT. UDAVA's distinctive approach capitalizes on domain-specific knowledge and leverages unsupervised learning and process mining techniques to tackle the formidable challenge of ensuring data quality and reliability in dynamic industrial environments. The pipeline encompasses a range of stages, including data preprocessing, cluster model creation, deviation metric calculation, sequence pruning, and event log generation. Systematically employing these stages, UDAVA adeptly addresses the intricacies of sensor data validation, offering a comprehensive solution that combines automated data processing with human-understandable event logs.

As part of the extension of UDAVA, we plan to integrate an automated configuration approach for UDAVA, leveraging Bayesian optimization and metamorphic testing, as demonstrated in our prior work on unsupervised anomaly detection. This will enable dynamic optimization of key parameters, such as window size and clustering algorithm selection, reducing reliance on manual tuning. Additionally, we aim to conduct a systematic comparison of UDAVA's unsupervised and semi-supervised modes, evaluating how manual annotations for cluster initialization impact clustering stability, anomaly detection, and process deviation analysis. This comparative study will help quantify the tradeoffs between fully automated pattern discovery and human-guided process validation, enhancing UDAVA's adaptability to diverse industrial scenarios.

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